

**OFF-AXIS STIFFNESS CHARACTERISATION OF
FIBRE-REINFORCED PLASTICS**

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ABSTRACT

Most of the current stiffness analysis techniques for fibre-reinforced plastics (FRP) are based on the assumption that the stiffness properties of FRP can be treated as orthotropic. For high ratios of fibre to matrix stiffnesses such an idealisation may be inappropriate and may not adequately describe all aspects of the material's deformation. This paper describes a more general characterisation, particularly applicable to those composites which have high stiffness fibres and low stiffness matrices such as resins. The approach avoids the assumption of orthotropic behaviour and instead treats the fibre composite as an inhomogeneous material with the fibres orientated at an arbitrary angle to the direction of the load. The individual and relative deformations of the fibres and the matrix are combined to give the total deformation of the composite. The deformation components considered include the rigid body rotation of the fibres towards the direction of the load. It is generally recognised that the experimental evaluation of FRP stiffness properties is very dependent on the test method used, particularly in the case of off-axis tests. The dead weight testing of off-axis tubular specimens has been investigated and results are compared to both the orthotropic and the new Rigid Body Motion characterisations.

KEYWORDS: Micromechanics; Stiffness Characterisation; Orthotropy; Inhomogeneity;
Test Method.

1. INTRODUCTION

A wide range of micromechanical theories have been developed to predict the elastic deformation of unidirectional fibre reinforced composite materials. These analytical techniques range from simple "strength of materials" approaches through to complicated "elasticity" solutions [1,2]. Virtually all of these theories have a common feature: they are used to predict the on-axis properties of a single ply of the fibre reinforced material. Once these on-axis properties are known the ply is treated as being macroscopically homogeneous and orthotropic, allowing the use of tensor stress and strain transformations to predict the off-axis properties.

The more sophisticated methods are fairly successful at predicting the on-axis properties of a unidirectional ply. Although the properties in the fibre direction can be accurately predicted, the transverse and particularly the shear properties are more difficult to model [1,2]. Semi-empirical approaches [3] can provide estimates of on-axis properties, and because of their relative simplicity are attractive for design use. However the difficulty in predicting the ply transverse and shear properties and the assumption of homogeneous, orthotropic behaviour does not always lead to accurate prediction of off axis ply properties [4,5,6].

This paper presents the basis of an alternative approach, intended for use in situations such as polymer matrix composites where the fibres and matrix have very different elastic properties. The model chosen treats the composite ply as being macroscopically inhomogeneous and considers the individual and relative deformations of the two components, thereby avoiding the assumption of orthotropy. In particular, the rigid body rotation of the fibre towards the direction of the load is included, hence this theory's Rigid Body Motion title. A full "elasticity" solution to the model chosen would be extremely complicated and thus of limited practical value. By taking a simplistic "mechanics of materials" approach it is intended that the solution be simple enough to be of practical value while maintaining acceptable accuracy.

In practice, it is difficult to make meaningful comparisons between the various analytical techniques used in the study of fibre composite deformation behaviour. The main reason for this difficulty lies in the shortage of reliable test data. Fibre composite test results are very dependent on the test method used, particularly in the case of off-axis tests. End constraints on the specimen can strongly influence measured results [7,8,9,10]. This paper briefly describes the dead weight testing of tubular specimens and compares the experimental results to both preliminary predictions from the Rigid Body Motion theory and more traditional micromechanical theories.

2. RIGID BODY MOTION MODEL

The model chosen to represent a fibre reinforced ply consists of an array of square fibres interspersed with rectangular matrix elements. The fibres are orientated at an arbitrary angle (θ) to the direction of the load (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Rigid Body Motion Model

The applied load is distributed between the fibre and the matrix, resulting in the following components of deformation:

- The fibres rotate ($\delta\theta$) towards the direction of the applied load.
- The fibres extend axially.
- The matrix deforms due to the load applied to it, displacing the fibres relative to each other.

These deformation components result in overall longitudinal, transverse and shear deformation of the composite element. (Figure 2). The fundamental difference to the orthotropic theory being the rigid body rotation of the fibre.

FIGURE 2. Deformed Rigid Body Motion Model
(Deformations greatly exaggerated)

In common with most other micromechanical theories [1] the following assumptions are made

- The fibres are linearly elastic and homogeneous.
- The matrix is linearly elastic and homogeneous.
- The composite is free of voids.
- There is complete bonding at the interface of the constituents and there is no transitional region between them.
- The ply is initially in a stress free state.
- The fibres are regularly spaced, straight, and are aligned.

In addition to these and the geometrical assumptions in Figure 1, the fundamental assumption of the Rigid Body Motion theory is that the fibre is much stiffer than the matrix, allowing the fibre to be treated as rigid in the direction of rotation.

The distribution of the overall load on the composite ply between the fibres and the matrix is modelled by considering equilibrium and continuity conditions. For more detailed information, and the exact form of the overall deformation model see Ref [11].

3. ROTATION COMPONENT

The basic premise of this analysis is that stiff fibres within a soft matrix will tend to rotate towards the direction of applied load (Figure 3). For the rotation analysis it is assumed that the relative stiffnesses of the components are such that the fibre can be treated as a rigid body. As shown in Figure 3, the load on each fibre can be resolved into two components, one in the longitudinal fibre direction and one transverse to it, the latter (P_{fT}) causing the rotation.

FIGURE 3. Rigid Body Rotation of Fibres

As the fibres rotate, the matrix between the fibres is deformed. The stresses generated by these strains in the matrix act on the fibre and resist the applied load. Consideration of the geometry changes in Figure 3 allows the strains in the matrix to be described as:

$$\epsilon_L = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_T = \frac{d_f(1 - \sin(\delta\theta)) + A_o \sin(\theta) \sin(\delta\theta)}{d_m} \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_{LT} = \frac{A_o \sin(\theta)(1 - \cos(\delta\theta)) - d_f \sin(\delta\theta) - \delta\theta d_m}{d_m} \quad (3)$$

The resulting stresses in the matrix can be related to the applied load by a strain energy approach, or by considering the force and moment equilibrium conditions for the fibre. Both yield almost identical results [11], the force / moment method being algebraically simpler. The resulting load vs rotation relationship is in the form of a quadratic in $\delta\theta$.

$$\delta\theta^2 A + \delta\theta B + C = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$A = \left(\begin{array}{l} d_f^3 \tan(\theta) - d_f^2 \frac{A_o}{2} (1 - \nu_m) \sin(\theta) + d_m d_f \tan(\theta) \left(d_f \nu_m + d_m (\nu_m - 1) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \\ - d_m d_f (1 - \nu_m) \sin(\theta) \left(\frac{A_o}{2} \cos(2\theta) - d_f \cos(\theta) \right) \end{array} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$B = \left(A_o^2 d_f \left(2 \sin^2(\theta) + (1 - \nu_m) \cos^2(\theta) \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

$$C = \left(\frac{2P(1 - \nu_m^2) d_m}{E_m} \right) \quad (7)$$

A finite element model was constructed of the rotation component. Different mesh densities were evaluated, the final model consisting of 100 plane stress quadratic elements. In addition to verifying the analytical solution [11], the finite element analysis also allowed the validity of the fibre rigidity assumption to be investigated. Figure 4 demonstrates the change in fibre rotation with variations in relative stiffness of the two components.

When fibre and matrix moduli are equal there is no rotation, both components undergoing shear only. As the fibre / matrix stiffness (E_f/E_m) increases, the rotation increases and the shear of the fibre decreases. With a typical glass / resin stiffness ratio of 20/1 there is approximately 5% difference between the actual rotation (Finite element) and that for the case of completely rigid fibres (Finite element and analytical). At a stiffness ratio of 100/1 (e.g. Boron / resin) there is virtually no difference to the completely rigid case.

FIGURE 4: Fibre Rotation vs Relative Modulus as Predicted by Finite Element Analysis

4. TESTING

The main difficulty in testing off axis fibre composites is caused by the coupling between different modes of deformation. In tensile testing the tension / shear coupling means that the selection of end fittings is critical [7,8,9,10]. Tubular specimens have the advantage that the ends of the specimen remain parallel, the tension / shear coupling resulting in twisting about the specimen's longitudinal axis. In torsion testing the converse is true, torsion of the tube resulting in a change of length. For meaningful tension test results it is necessary to apply an axial load to the specimen while allowing it complete freedom to twist. With torsion testing it is necessary to apply torque to the specimen while allowing it complete freedom to change in length.

Both tension and torsion tests can be valid methods of obtaining the off axis properties of fibre reinforced materials. In this work both methods were investigated and attempts were made to develop attachments which would allow specimen testing in standard testing machines. None of the mechanical techniques tried were successful in achieving acceptable freedom of rotation or extension. More sophisticated and expensive methods using hydraulics or pneumatics were considered but rejected on the grounds of cost and uncertainty of success.

The simple, but effective technique which was used in this research is shown in Figure 5. The tubular specimen is suspended vertically from a load cell and loaded with lead masses. The "dead weight" of the masses applies an axial tension load to the specimen and is completely free to rotate as the specimen twists. To avoid problems associated with strain gauges such as cross-sensitivity, Linear Variable Differential Transformers (LVDT's) are used to measure extension and twist of the tube.

The specimens were manufactured from a 50% fibre volume fraction glass/polyester prepreg with 90% of the fibres in one direction and 10% at 90 degrees to it. The helix angle of the 90% fibres was varied from 0 to 55 degrees. The specimens had an inside diameter of 25.4 mm, approximately 3.2 mm wall thickness and a length of 400 mm. Loads of up to 4000 N were applied to the tubes.

The main disadvantage of this test method is that it is relatively time consuming. The specimens were also more expensive to manufacture than smaller and simpler specimens. However this method of testing did avoid most of the end constraint problems associated with conventional test methods and should allow more accurate determination of the off-axis properties.

FIGURE 5. Dead Weight Test Method

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some preliminary results from the "Rigid Body Motion" (RBM) model are presented in Figures 6 and 7. The "Rigid Body Motion" results are compared to the "Rule Of Mixtures" (ROM) orthotropic solution [3] and to experimental results at an equal load. The "Rule Of Mixtures" solution is used as a comparison because it is developed from similar assumptions to the "Rigid Body Motion" theory. Sophisticated and semi-empirical theories can more accurately model observed behaviour than the "Rule Of Mixtures", but their comparisons to the "Rigid Body Motion" theory are deemed to be inappropriate at this stage.

FIGURE 6. Longitudinal Strain vs Fibre Angle

FIGURE 7. Shear Strain vs Fibre Angle

Meaningful comparisons of the "Rigid Body Motion" and "Rule of Mixtures" theories with the experimental results are difficult to make for two reasons. Although the 10% of fibres at 90 degrees to the principal fibre direction is not very significant at small fibre angles it does make a large difference to the ply stiffness at larger fibre angles. At a principal fibre angle of 55 degrees the classical laminated plate theory predicts longitudinal strains approximately 15% less than those with 100% of fibres at the same fibre angle. Neither of the analytical solutions, as presented here, account for this. Current work on test specimens with 100% of fibres in the principal direction is in progress.

A problem common to all micromechanical theories is the determination of the constituent properties. Either attempts are made to test components individually or their properties are back calculated from measured ply on-axis properties. In this case the fibre properties were estimated from the on-axis ply properties. Results have been presented for different matrix stiffnesses to highlight the matrix's large effect on the off-axis properties of the ply. In both Figures 6 and 7 a relatively small change in the matrix stiffness greatly changes the predicted ply properties.

It is significant in Figure 6 that the "Rigid Body Motion" model's predictions approach those of the "Rule of Mixtures" as the matrix stiffness increases. This trend agrees with the findings presented in Figure 4 which shows that the rotation component becomes important when there is a large difference between the elastic stiffnesses of the two constituents.

There is less agreement between the two models in the case of the shear strain, Figure 7. This is expected because the fibre rotation is more significant in determining the shear strain than the longitudinal strain. However it is premature to conclude too much from this case because the "Rigid Body Motion" model is still not fully developed. In particular, the distribution of component loads is being refined and may affect the amount of rotation predicted.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A "Rigid Body Motion" micromechanics model for the stiffness properties of off-axis fibre reinforced plastics has been presented. Although relatively simple, and still in its uncompleted stage, the model's predictions do have reasonable agreement with experimental results. The model's predictions of deformations differ from those of the traditional micromechanics models. The difference is particularly significant when there is a large difference in the constituents' elastic stiffnesses. The "Rigid Body Motion" model can be considered to provide an off-axis "Rule Of Mixtures" without the assumption of homogeneous and orthotropic ply behaviour.

7. NOMENCLATURE

θ	Fibre Angle	Subscripts:
$\delta\theta$	Fibre Rotation Angle	
$P_{i,j}$	Loads	1,2 Cartesian Axes for Loads
$\epsilon_{i,j}$	Strains	L,T Cartesian Axes for Ply
E	Modulus	f Fibre
ν	Poisson's Ratio	m Matrix
d	Representative Diameter	
A_0	Spacing of Fibres = $(d_f + d_m) / \cos(\theta)$	

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